

COMPARISON OF LEAD – ARSENATE GLASSES DOPED WITH V_2O_5 AND Sm_2O_3

¹ K. Lokeswara rao, ² P.ES.Bhaskar, ³ A. Chittibabu, ⁴ G. Lalitha devi

¹Assistant professor, ²Assistant professor, ³Assistant professor, ⁴Lecturer

¹Department of Physics,

¹Ramachandra college of engineering, Eluru, India

² Department of Physics,

² Ramachandra college of engineering, Eluru, India

³ Department of Physics,

³ Krishna university, Machilipatnam, India

⁴ Department of Physics,

⁴ Sir CRR college (A), Eluru, India

Abstract : Glasses with compositions $(40 - x) PbO - 60 As_2O_3 \cdot x V_2O_5$ and Sm_2O_3 with $x=0, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8$ and 1 mol% were prepared by conventionally melt quenching technique. Various physical properties are calculated like density, molar volume, polran radius, interionic distance and field strength. Spectroscopic properties characterized by these glasses viz, In the PL spectra with increase in the concentration of V_2O_5 , the intensity of the peak is observed to increase to a red shift. The emission spectra exhibited four bands and the calculated color coordinates for the present glasses fall well within the reddish-orange region of the CIE diagram.

1. INTRODUCTION

The study on the influence of vanadyl ions in As_2O_3 glasses has been the subject of extensive investigations into the recent years. These glasses has exponentially high Raman scattering coefficients and found to be suitable for acting fiber Raman applications [1]. As_2O_3 is the most important oxide of Arsenic and is obtained by burning in the air [2, 3] or by the hydrolysis of $AsCl_3$ [4]. The basic structural unit in As_2O_3 at temperatures below $800^\circ C$ is the As_2O_3 Pyramid. In the Vapour Phase below $800^\circ C$ four As_2O_3 units share (oxygen) Corners to form the As_4O_6 molecule [5, 6]. An alternative way of viewing this molecule is as a tetrahedral As_4 molecule with each As-As bond replaced by an As-O-As bridging oxygen atoms, oxygen atoms being arranged at the vertices of the regular octahedrons. Solid As_2O_3 is interesting material in that, it exists on the crystalline state as both a molecular solid and as to polymers having an infinite layer Structure. The structure of arsenolite is similar to that of diamond with each carbon atom is replaced by an As_4O_6 molecule the molecules on the two sub lattices being rotated by $\pi/2$ relative to each other [7]. Deep network former is As_2O_3 with corner sharing AsO_3 pyramids; earlier neutron diffraction studies indicates that normal bond lengths As-O lie between $1.72-1.81 \text{ \AA}$ and O-As -O and As-O-As bond angles lie in the range $90-103^\circ$, and $123-135^\circ$ respectively [8].

Addition of PbO to these glasses makes them to be relatively moisture resistant and also lowers the rate of crystallization, since PbO, has the capability to form steady glasses due to its matched-one as alterter, if Pb-O is ionic and the Variant -as glass former, if Pb-O is covalent [9, 10]. When Pb^{2+} ions are existent in the glass as network formers a three-dimensional character of the glass. This certainty statement by the capability of PbO to form glasses up to 90 mol % s clearly the peculiar behavior, which distinguishes lead from alkali and alkaline earth metals, build upon the electronic structure of the Pb^{2+} ion. In fact the easily polarizable valence shell of the Pb^{2+} ion strongly interacts with also highly polarizable O^{2-} ion, giving rise to a rather covalent Pb-O bond [11].

Now a day's rare earth (RE) doped glasses is very useful information about Fiber amplifiers, up converters, Light emitting Diodes (LED'S), Optical fibers, Wave guide laser and Fluorescent display devices (12-14). Many Researchers are focused on RE^{3+} doped glasses to give a valuable information about visible optical devices (15-16). In generally, the optical and spectroscopic studies of RE ions are strongly dependent on host materials. One of the chosen host materials is oxide glasses which is chemically durability, thermally; optically transparent at the excitation and lasing wave lengths (17).

Sm^{3+} ions are more significant, various fluorescent devices and visible laser (18-19). Comparing to other rare-earth ions Sm^{3+} doped laser materials have many advantages and exhibit small emission efficiencies (20-21). The optical properties of RE ions with chemical Environment and this has been tested for Sm^{3+} in different hosts (22-26). Samarium has promised characteristics for spectral hole burning studies (27-28).

Preferably wide radial dispersal and their responses to surrounding actions are very sensitive; as a result these ions influence the physical Properties of the glasses to a long -lasting scope.

In concept of these, it is felt worthwhile to have some interpretation of the Spectroscopic properties of PbO- As_2O_3 glasses containing another transition metal ion i.e. vanadium. V_2O_5 is known to join in the glass network of VO_5 pyramidal structural

units. Several vanadate glasses shows semiconducting behavior with the electrical conductivity of 10^{-3} to 10^{-5} ($\Omega\text{-cm}$)⁻¹, which is known to be electron hopping between V^{4+} to V^{5+} ions, existing on the glass network. Further, vanadium glasses are identified as the n- type semiconductors for low value of the V^{4+} / V^{5+} ratio. The vanadium ions may more over prevailing on the glass network of V^{2+} and V^{3+} states [29].The investigations into spectroscopic (viz., optical absorption, photoluminescence, infrared spectra and electron spin resonance) give the information on the position and oxidation states of the transition metal ions in the glass network and help to assess the suitability of these glasses for practical applications.

In the present investigations Sm^{3+} ions doped with $PbO\text{-}As_2O_3$ glasses. As_2O_3 is very strong network former, it's exhibiting high Raman scattering coefficient and low-loss materials for long-distance optical transmission (30-32).Several studies on As_2O_3 glasses mixed with alkali halides, rare earth oxides and some heavy metal oxides (33-37).Certain studies on As_2O_3 glasses mixed with different Semiconducting oxides viz; GeO_2 , V_2O_5 , SiO_2 etc are also available (38-40).Hybridization effect on mechanical properties on and erosion and wear of epoxy glass composites (41). An addition of PbO,As_2O_3 glasses are observed moisture resistant and low rates of crystallization.

2. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

V_2O_5 doped $PbO\text{-}As_2O_3$ glasses was prepared; using melt-quenching technique . The content of vanadium in the glass composition is varied from 0.2 to 1.0 mol% s. The details of glass compositions chosen for the present to study are listed in table-1.The starting materials used for the preparation of the present glasses were analytical grade reagents (99.9 % pure) of PbO , As_2O_3 , and V_2O_5 . The compounds of required compositions were thoroughly mixed in an agate mortar and melted in a platinum crucible. The furnace cast-of was a PID temperature superintending a furnace. The glasses was melted at about 600 - 650 °C s for a half an hour till a bubble free liquid was formed. The development rendered was flowed on a rectangular brass mould (carrying velvety gloosy inside surface) held at room temperature. The samples were subsequently annealed at 250 °C s in another furnace. The glasses was then ground and idiotically gleaming. The approximate final dimensions of the glasses used for studying the electrical and optical properties are 1 cm x 1 cm x0.2 cm.

A series of $PbO\text{-}As_2O_3$ glasses doped with samarium ions (Sm^{3+}) were prepared by conventional melt quenching technique in the compositions of $(40-x)PbO\text{-}60 As_2O_3\text{-} xSm_2O_3$ (where $x = 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8$ and 1.0%) are listed Table 1.The raw materials of lead oxide (PbO), Arsenic trioxide (As_2O_3) and Samarium oxide (Sm_2O_3) of appropriate amounts are mixed together and melted in silica crucible at a temperature of 600-650°C for 10 to 15 min until a bubble free liquid has been formed. The resultant melt was then poured in a brass mould and subsequently annealed from 200°C with a cooling rate 1 °C/min .Then the samples are finely polished to final dimensions 1 cm x 1 cm x 0.2 cm for the measurements .The photoluminescence spectra of glasses were recorded on Photon Technology International fluorescence spectrophotometer in UV and NIR regions with a monochromator and photomultiplier tube for detecting the luminescence response in the appropriate wavelength regions. By using Archimedes's principle, the density d of the glasses was determined to an accuracy of ± 0.001 by means of o-xylene (99.99% pure) as the buoyant liquid.3. Results by means of conventional formulae and practically measured density, various physical parameters .

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Physical Parameters

Density and refractive index are important physical parameters of the glasses, more over these are useful to estimate other important physical parameters such as Vanadium and Samarium ion concentration (N_i), mean separation (r_i), Polaron radius (r_p), field strength (F_i), electronic polarizability (α_e), reflection loss as well as optical dielectric constant (ϵ_0) in the present glass network. The predictable formulae used for the estimation of these parameters.For Vanadium doped glasses with increasing of mol % polaron radius decreased ,Field strength increased as shown in Fig.1. With increasing of mol % density increased, molar volume decreased as shown in Fig.2. With increasing of mol % density increased, as shown in Fig.3. For Samarium doped glasses with increasing of mol % density decreased, as shown in Fig.4. With increasing of mol % density decreased ,molar volume increased as shown in Fig.5.With increasing of mol % polaron radius decreased, Field strength increased as shown in Fig.6.

Table 1: Glass compositions of $PbO\text{-}As_2O_3$ glasses doped with V_2O_5 & Sm_2O_3

Glass code	As_2O_3 (mol %)	PbO (mol %)	V_2O_5 & Sm_2O_3 (mol %)
V_0 & Sm_0	60	40	0
V_2 & $Sm_{0.2}$	60	39.8	0.2
V_4 & $Sm_{0.4}$	60	39.6	0.4
V_6 & $Sm_{0.6}$	60	39.4	0.6
V_8 & $Sm_{0.8}$	60	39.2	0.8
V_{10} & $Sm_{1.0}$	60	39	1.0

Table 2: various physical parameters of PbO-As₂O₃ glasses doped with V₂O₅

Glass	Density d (g/cm ³)	Avg.Mol. weight ($\bar{M}$)	Conc.of V ⁵⁺ ions Ni (10 ²¹ /cm ³)	Inter ionic distance r _i (A°)	Polaron radius r _p (A°)	Field strength F, (x10 ¹⁵ cm ⁻²)	Molar volume (V _m)
V ₂	5.1631	207.90	2.99	6.94	2.79	6.42	40.26
V ₄	5.1930	207.81	6.02	5.49	2.21	10.23	40.01
V ₆	5.5525	207.73	9.66	4.69	1.89	13.99	37.41
V ₈	5.6985	207.65	13.2	4.23	1.70	17.30	36.43
V ₁₀	5.7250	207.57	16.8	3.89	1.57	20.28	36.25

Table 3: various physical parameters of PbO-As₂O₃ glasses doped with Sm₂O₃

Glass	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8	1.0
Density d (g/cm ³)	5.999	5.976	5.956	5.931	5.902
Avg.Mol. Weight ($\bar{M}$)	208.235	208.486	208.737	208.988	209.239
Conc.of Sm ³⁺ ions N _i (10 ²¹ /cm ³)	3.47	6.905	10.311	13.674	16.981
Inter ionic distance r _i (A°)	6.6052	5.2514	4.594	4.1818	3.8837
Polaron radius r _p (A°)	2.66	2.11	1.85	1.68	1.56
Field strength F, (x10 ¹⁵ cm ⁻²)	4.239	6.738	8.765	10.629	12.327
Refractive index(n)	1.777	1.765	1.758	1.741	1.731
Reflection loss	0.418	0.413	0.410	0.403	0.399
Molar volume (V _m)	34.711	34.887	35.046	35.236	35.4522
Molar refraction (R _m)	14.5097	14.4064	14.3688	14.2052	14.1454
Molar electronic polarizability(α _m) (A°) ³	5.754	5.713	5.698	5.633	5.609
Metallization factor(M)	0.581	0.587	0.599	0.596	0.601

Fig.1.Mol % Vs Field Strength and Polaron Radius

Fig.2.Mol % Vs Density and Molar Volume

Fig.3.Mol % Vs Density

Fig.4.Mol % Vs Density

Fig.5.Mol % Vs Density and Molar Volume

Fig.6.Mol % Vs Field Strength and Polaron Radius

3.2 Photoluminescence spectra

Fig.7. shows the photoluminescence spectra of PbO-As₂O₃ glasses recorded at room temperature with excitation wavelength of 645 nm. The spectrum of each glass exhibits a broad emission band of the region 765-775 nm; this bands is identified due to ²E→²T₂ transition to vanadyl ion, the band exhibits a slight asymmetry in the higher wavelength region. With the growing content of V₂O₅ in the glass matrix, the half width of the peak are observed to increase.

The tunability of color emitted by the glass samples, the variation in the relative intensities of the emission bands has been analyzed in the CIE diagram, The diagram exhibits all the chromaticity visible to the human eye.Fig.8 shows the CIE (1931)

chromaticity co-ordinates of Sm^{3+} doped $\text{PbO-As}_2\text{O}_3$ glasses under 403.2 nm excitations. The evaluated chromaticity coordinates (x,y) are (0.577,0.417), (0.580,0.409), (0.587,0.405), (0.593,0.396), (0.599,0.388) for Sm^{3+} doped $\text{PbO-As}_2\text{O}_3$ glasses ($\text{Sm}0.2, \text{Sm}0.4, \text{Sm}0.6, \text{Sm}0.8, \text{Sm}1.0$) respectively. These coordinates are very useful in determining the exact color of the sample. Fig.8 represents CIE diagram of Sm^{3+} doped $\text{PbO-As}_2\text{O}_3$ glasses.

Fig. 7. Emission spectra of $\text{PbO-As}_2\text{O}_3: \text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ glasses

Fig.8. The CIE chromaticity diagram of $\text{PbO-As}_2\text{O}_3:\text{Sm}_2\text{O}_3$ glasses

4. Conclusions

$\text{PbO-As}_2\text{O}_3: x\text{V}_2\text{O}_5$ and $\text{Sm}_2\text{O}_3(x: 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0)$ (mol %) glasses were prepared by adopting melt-quenching technique. Various physical parameters are estimated with the help of experimental densities and refractive index. For Vanadium glasses exhibit a broad emission band of the region 765-775 nm; this bands is identified due to ${}^2E \rightarrow {}^2T_2$ transition to vanadyl ion, the band exhibits a slight asymmetry in the higher wavelength region, In the PL spectra with increase in the concentration of V_2O_5 , the intensity of the peak is observed to increase to a red shift. The emission spectra exhibited four bands and the calculated color coordinates for the present glasses fall well within the reddish-orange region of the CIE diagram.

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